

EIC User Group Newsletter

September 2020

Prepared by

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NEWS

- The [3rd Yellow Report Workshop](#) at CUA (Washington) was held **online on 16-18 September**. On the [first day](#) several talks of **update** were delivered about the **status of the EIC Project** and of the international engagement, followed by 12 **short presentations** from teams **submitting their Expression of Interest (EoI)**. The session was concluded by a thorough discussion on **detector complementarity** and related technical aspects. On the [second day](#), the morning session was devoted to **update reports** from the Physics Working Groups (**PWG**), followed in the afternoon by a **overview of detector configurations** by the Detector Working Groups (**DWG**), and by presentations on technical problems related to the accelerator design. On the [third day](#), the morning session was dedicated to the **writing process of the Yellow Report** document (structure, timeline, etc.); in the afternoon, results of the [Charter Committee's survey](#) were commented, the [next steps of the EIC Project Management](#) were discussed, and finally the [proposal for a series of CFNS Workshops](#) focussed on a **second Interaction Region** at the EIC was presented. All material can be found at the [Indico agenda](#).
- On **Sept. 18**, the event “**Electron-Ion Collider Project Launch**” was held at BNL, with a limited participation due to Covid-19 restrictions, and with online contributions from representatives of (international) major institutions (including CERN General Director F. Gianotti). More details can be found [here](#), including a link to a Youtube video of the ceremony.

- In the [“Yellow Report” menu of the EICUG web page](#), one can find the **calendar** of the last **“Yellow Report” workshop**, to be held **online**:
 4. 18-20 November 2020, UCB - Berkeley (USA)

NEWS from the CONFERENCE & TALKS COMMITTEE

- A **new Conference & Talks Committee** has been appointed:
 - Sevil Salur (Rutgers)
 - Dmitry Romanov (JLab)
 - Michela Chiosso (Univ. Torino)
 - Svetlana Barkanova (Memorial Univ. of Newfoundland)
 - Alexey Prokudin (PSU - Berks)
- The community welcomes the new members, Michela Chiosso, Svetlana Barkanova and Alexey Prokudin, and warmly thanks Barbara Pasquini, Carlos Munoz Camacho, and Ralf Seidl for having served on this Committee.
- Because of the Covid-19 lockdown, the **schedule** of next workshops and summer schools of interest for the EICUG has been **drastically modified**: many events have been **postponed** (sometimes with tentative dates), have **become on-line** meetings, or have been **cancelled** completely (see below). Thus, the speaking opportunities on behalf of the EICUG have been reduced. Nevertheless, there is **still the available opportunity** to give a talk (either on line or in person) at:
 1. [IWHSS2020](#), Trieste (Italy), 16-18 November 2020
- In any case, for consulting the list of **open EICUG talks** see <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/open> . For a list of **previous EICUG talks** see <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/previous> (often including also a link to the presentation). If you wish to recommend a candidate, including yourself, or if in general you wish to suggest new speakers (including yourself) to be considered for future invitations, please contact the Conference & Talks Committee at eicug-talks@eicug.org . Here, you can find also the general [talks guidelines](#) .

NEWS from the CHARTER COMMITTEE

- The Charter Committee has surveyed the entire Users Group with respect to some important issues about the EICUG organization, effectiveness of communications, voting procedures, etc.. The survey closed on Sept. 1st. A total of 102 responses were received. The **results of the survey** was presented by Richard Milner, Chair of the Charter Committee, at the 3rd “Yellow Report” CUA Workshop, and can be found [here](#).

NEWS from the ELECTION & NOMINATION COMMITTEE

- A **new Election & Nomination Committee** has been appointed:
 - Marta Ruspa (Univ. Piemonte Orientale) Chair
 - Abhay Deshpande (SBU / BNL)
 - Yuri Kovchegov (OSU)
 - Douglas Higinbotham (JLab)
 - Charlotte Van Hulse (IPN-Orsay)
- The community welcomes the new members, Douglas Higinbotham and Charlotte Van Hulse, and warmly thanks Paul Newman and Christian Weiss for having served on this Committee.

NEWS from the INSTITUTIONAL BOARD

- The **EICUG** currently stands at **1175 members**, from **241 institutions** in **32 countries**. Theory members are approximately 25%, experimentalists 61%, experts in accelerators 13%, support 1%.
- Since previous Newsletter, **three more institutions** joined the EICUG:
 - * University of Amsterdam (Netherlands)
 - * Eotvos University (Hungary)
 - * Central University of Tamil Nadu (India)

RECENT WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

See also <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/previous> (includes also links to some presentations)

Those events labeled by were held with on-line only format.

[40th International Conference on High Energy Physics \(ICHEP 2020\)](#), Prague (Czech Republic), 28 July - 6 August 2020

[Hadron Collider Physics Summer School](#), Fermilab-CERN, 10-21 August 2020

[Silicon pixel-based particle vertex and tracking detectors towards the US Electron-Ion Collider Workshop](#), 2-4 September 2020

[9th International Conference on New Frontiers in Physics \(ICNFP 2020\)](#), Kolymbary (Crete - Greece), 4 - 12 September 2020

[EIC Lepton Polarimetry Expression of Interest](#), 15 September 2020

[Online Joint GlueX-EIC-PANDA Machine Learning Workshop](#), 21-25 September 2020

[Backward-Angle \(u-channel\) Physics Workshop](#), JLab, 21-23 September 2020

[Data Science Roadmap to Compton Form Factors of Quarks and Gluons](#), ODU (Virginia-US), 24-25 September 2020

[Future Trends in Nuclear Physics Computing](#), 29 September - 1 October 2020

[Target Fragmentation Physics with EIC](#), CFNS (Stonybrook-US) 28-30 September 2020

UPCOMING WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

See also <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/upcoming> and <http://cnr2.kent.edu/~manley/BRAGmeetings.html> (the latter is temporarily not updated due to the current “stay at home” order)

The events labeled by will be held only on-line. If joined by “?”, it means that a decision is not yet taken.

[Origin of the Visible Universe: Unraveling the Proton Mass \(INT-20-77W\)](#), INT Seattle (WA - US), 4 - 8 May 2020 **Postponed**

[Transversity 2020](#), Pavia (Italy), 25-29 May 2020
Postponed to May 2021

[Tomography of light nuclei at an EIC](#), ECT*-Trento (Italy), 15-19 June 2020 **Postponed** to 25-29 October 2021

[LXX International Conference NUCLEUS-2020](#), Saint Petersburg (Russia), 26-30 June 2020 **Postponed** to 11-17 October 2020 ?

[Light-Cone 2020 \(LC2020\)](#), Jeju (Korea), 29 June - 4 July 2020
Postponed to 5-10 July 2021 as **LC2021**

[22nd International Conference on Particles and Nuclei \(PANIC2020\)](#), Lisbon (Portugal), 31 August - 4 September 2020
Postponed to 30 August - 3 September 2021

[24th International Spin Symposium SPIN2020](#), Matsue (Japan), 20-25 September 2020 **Postponed** to fall 2021

[Baryon 2020](#), Sevilla (Spain), 22-25 September 2020
Postponed to 19-22 October 2021 as **Baryon 2021**

[New Physics Phenomena - Hadronic Contributions to New Physics Searches](#), Crete (Greece), 24-30 September 2020 **Postponed** Spring 2021

[5th International Conference on Particle Physics and Astrophysics \(ICCPA 2020\)](#), Moscow (Russia), 5-9 October 2020

[APS DNP Fall meeting](#), 29 October - 1 November 2020

[Opportunities with Heavy Flavor at the EIC](#), CFNS (Stonybrook-US), 4-6 November 2020

- [The 17th International Workshop on Hadron Structure and Spectroscopy \(IWHSS 2020\)](#), Trieste (Italy), 16-18 November 2020 ?
- [Jets for 3D imaging at the EIC](#), Riverside (CA-US), 17-18 November 2020
- [Fast Machine Learning for Science Workshop](#), Southern Methodist Univ. (US), 30 November - 3 December 2020
- [Resummation, Evolution, Factorization \(REF 2020\)](#), Univ. Edinburgh (Scotland), 7-11 December 2020
- [8th International Conference on High Energy Physics in the LHC era](#), Valparaiso (Chile), 4-8 January 2021
- [EIC Physics in the Snowmass process](#), CFNS (Stonybrook-US), 11-15 January 2021
- [Forward Physics and QCD with LHC, EIC and cosmic rays](#), 20-23 January 2021
- [Open questions in photon-induced interactions - From relativistic nuclear collisions to the EIC](#), CFNS (Stonybrook-US), 26-29 April 2021 ?
- [RHIC Science programs informative toward the EIC in the coming years](#), CFNS (Stonybrook-US), 24-27 May 2021 ?
- [QCD Evolution 2021 Workshop](#), UCLA (US), 10-14 May 2021
- [2nd workshop on Jets for 3D imaging at the EIC](#), CFNS (Stonybrook-US), 16-18 June 2021 ?
- [The XIVth Quark Confinement and the Hadron Spectrum Conference](#), Stavanger (Norway), 2-7 August 2021
- [Lepton-Photon 2021](#), Manchester (UK), 9-14 August 2021
- [Experimental applications of Artificial Intelligence for the EIC \(AI4EIC-Ex\)](#), CFNS (Stonybrook-US), 6-10 September 2021 ?
- Quarks and Nucleon Physics (QNP 2021), Bonn (Germany), 20-24 September 2021
- [Workshop on the QCD Structure of the Nucleon \(QCD-N2021\)](#), Univ. Alcalà (Spain), 4-8 October 2021

UPCOMING SCHOOLS of INTEREST

[MCnet-CTEQ Summer School 2020](#), Bad Herrenalb (Germany), 2-12 August 2020 **Cancelled**

[International School for Strangeness Nuclear Physics](#)
(SNP2020), J-PARC, Tokai (Japan), 2-5 December 2020

